

Synthesis and Biological Activity of some New 2*H*,5*H*-3,4-Dihydro-8- and 9-Methyl[1]benzopyrano[3,4-*e*]-1,3-oxazin-5-ones

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Benzopyranones have been reported to possess various biological activities¹. In continuation of our study on the synthesis and pharmacological activities of substituted 2*H*-1-benzopyran-2-ones², we now report the synthesis of some new structurally related 2*H*-1-benzopyran-2-ones (3 and 4a-j) with a view to evaluating their biological activities. The structures of the compounds have been ascertained from their uv, ir, ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectral data.

The starting compounds 4-hydroxy-6-methyl- and 7-methyl-2*H*-1-benzopyran-2-ones (1 and 2 respectively) were synthesised according to the reported method³. Compounds 1 and 2 on treatment separately with paraformaldehyde and primary amine⁴ in the presence of base gave compounds 3a-j and 4a-j respectively.

1, 3; R = CH₃, R' = H
2, 4; R = H, R' = CH₃

Results and Discussion

The ir bands for hydroxyl (3 373 cm⁻¹) observed for 1 and 2 were absent in the spectra of 3a-j and 4a-j, thus showing the participation of the hydroxyl group in the oxazino ring formation. Likewise, the signals for C(3)-H (δ 5.65) and hydroxyl (δ 7.5) observed in the ¹H nmr spectra of 1 and 2 were

absent in the spectra of 3a-j and 4a-j indicating the formation of ring system at 3- and 4-positions of the pyrone ring system. The ¹³C nmr data of 3 and 4a, d, j were assigned on the basis of those reported for other benzopyranones⁵. Utilising the substituent chemical shift values the C-4a and C-1a of these compounds have been assigned the values of δ 102.52 and 164.85, respectively.

Among the compounds screened, the compounds with *p*-chlorophenyl, *p*-bromophenyl and *p*-tolyl substituents at C-3 showed highest antibacterial activity. In the antifungal screening, the *p*-chlorophenyl, *p*-bromophenyl, *p*-tolyl and *p*-anisyl derivatives were found to be more effective against both the fungi at 200 ppm concentration.

Experimental

Melting points were determined by open capillary method on Mel-Temp and are uncorrected. Uv spectra (95% ethanol) were recorded on a Shimadzu 160-A spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 983 G spectrophotometer and ¹H (90 and 400 MHz) and ¹³C nmr (100 MHz) spectra (CDCl₃) on Bruker FT spectrometers using TMS as internal standard.

2*H*, 5*H*-3,4-Dihydro-9-methyl[1]benzopyrano[3,4-*e*]-1,3-oxazin-5-ones (3a-j): A solution of paraformaldehyde (2.4 g, 0.8 mol) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) containing potassium hydroxide (0.03 g) was prepared by gentle warming. To this solution, appropriate amine (0.04 mol) was added portionwise with cooling, followed by compound 1 (0.04 mol) and absolute ethanol (10 ml) and the mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath for 3-4 h. The resulting solid on cooling or on solvent removal was crystallised from suitable solvent.

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	R''	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	¹ H chemical shifts (δ)			
				H ₂ ^a	H ₄ ^b	C ₅ -/C ₉ -CH ₃	H _{phenyl} ^{**}
3a	Phenyl	160-62	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ NO ₃	4.6	4.4	2.4	6.8-7.4
b	β-Phenylethyl	142-44	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ NO ₃	4.5	4.3	2.4	6.8-7.4
c	p-Tolyl	175-76	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ NO ₃	4.4	4.2	2.3	6.9-7.3
d	m-Tolyl	172	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ NO ₃	4.7	4.4	2.4	7.0-7.3
e	p-Methoxyphenyl	151	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ NO ₄	4.8	4.3	2.3	7.0-7.4
f	o-Methoxyphenyl	145-46	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ NO ₄	4.6	4.5	2.4	6.9-7.3
g	p-Bromophenyl	166	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ NO ₃ Br	4.8	4.4	2.4	6.8-7.3
h	p-Chlorophenyl	128	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ NO ₃ Cl	4.7	4.5	2.3	7.2-7.5
i	m-Chlorophenyl	135	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ NO ₃ Cl	4.6	4.3	2.3	6.9-7.3
j	Benzyl	148-50	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ NO ₃	4.4	4.2	2.4	6.8-7.4
4a	Phenyl	159	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ NO ₃	4.6	4.4	2.4	6.8-7.4
b	β-Phenylethyl	140	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ NO ₃	4.5	4.3	2.2	6.8-7.4
c	p-Tolyl	170-72	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ NO ₃	4.4	4.2	2.3	6.9-7.3
d	m-Tolyl	169-70	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ NO ₃	4.7	4.4	2.4	7.0-7.3
e	p-Methoxyphenyl	148	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ NO ₄	4.8	4.3	2.4	7.0-7.4
f	o-Methoxyphenyl	140	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ NO ₄	4.6	4.5	2.3	6.9-7.3
g	p-Bromophenyl	152-54	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ NO ₃ Br	4.8	4.4	2.3	6.8-7.3
h	p-Chlorophenyl	120	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ NO ₃ Cl	4.7	4.5	2.2	7.2-7.5
i	m-Chlorophenyl	129	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ NO ₃ Cl	4.6	4.3	2.2	6.9-7.3
j	Benzyl	138-40	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ NO ₃	4.4	4.2	2.4	6.8-7.4

*Appeared as (2H, s) in each spectrum; C₇, H₃, H₉ and C₁₀-proton signals merged in the aromatic multiplet. **Phenyl protons appeared as (5H, m) in a, b, j and as (4H, m) in c-f compounds; 3b, N-CH₂-CH₂-Ph, 3.4-3.5 (4H, m); 3c and d, Ar-CH₃, 2.2 (3H, s); 3e, f, Ar-OCH₃, 4.1 (3H, s); 3j, Ar-CH₂, 3.6 (2H, s); same values were observed in the corresponding 4 compounds.

TABLE 2—¹³C NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF COMPOUNDS*

Carbon number	3a	3b	3c	4a	4b	4c
C-2	68.55	69.22	68.55	70.85	69.75	70.21
C-4	58.22	59.52	58.85	60.85	69.75	71.21
C-5	162.82	161.75	161.52	161.82	161.75	162.90
C-7	117.00	116.82	116.59	116.98	117.25	116.39
C-8	133.89	139.52	136.52	138.97	139.25	140.12
C-9	132.33	124.37	126.22	124.64	125.22	125.12
C-10	124.77	124.15	124.68	124.21	124.72	124.26
C-1a	164.85	165.12	164.68	163.85	164.57	163.86
C-4a	102.52	103.12	102.58	102.45	103.11	102.34
C-6a	148.66	153.51	150.96	147.92	148.21	146.98
C-10a	119.96	117.45	120.34	117.92	118.85	117.85
C-8/	21.04	21.56	21.00	21.50	21.48	21.06
C-9/CH ₃						
C-1'	147.00	132.85	148.83	147.00	132.85	148.83
C-2'	113.72	129.05	110.78	113.72	129.05	110.78
C-3'	129.20	129.05	119.03	129.20	129.05	119.03
C-4'	118.11	129.05	143.52	118.11	129.05	142.52
C-5'	129.20	129.05	129.08	129.20	129.05	129.08
C-6'	113.72	129.05	114.68	113.72	129.05	114.68

*Number of carbons as reported earlier (Ref. 6); C-4'-CH₃ (21.58); N-CH₂-CH₂, (a, 45.25; b 59.12).

Compounds 4a-j were prepared in a similar manner.

Activity of the title compounds was evaluated by the reported method⁷ at 100 ppm concentration against the bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Streptococcus aureus* and at 100 and 200 ppm

concentrations against the fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Helminthosporium oryzae*.

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